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Bioactivity and Application of Gamal Leaves (*Gliricidia Maculata*) As a Biofungicide against Phytopathogenic Fungi in Chili Pepper (*Capsicum Annum L.*)

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Abstract

The aim of this study was to determine the effective concentration of gamal (*Gliricidia maculata*) leaf extract against several pathogenic fungi (*Colletotrichum capsici*, *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Cercospora capsici*) in Chili paper plantation. There were two main stages of activities in conducting this research namely, *in vitro* using a Non-Factorial Completely Randomized Design (RAL Non-Factorial) and *in-vivo* analysis. The treatment was performed by using non-factorial complete design, it was found that the factors that became the treatment level were the provision of gamal leaf extract consisting of 30 – 100% gamal leaf extract treatment. Furthermore, an experiment was carried out *in vivo* using a non-factorial randomized block design (non-factorial shelf). Based on the result effective dosage for controlling pathogenic fungi (*Colletotrichum capsici*, *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Cercospora capsici*) was 20% gamal leaf extract, the highest inhibition percentage of *Colletotrichum capsici* was 82.49%, at a concentration of ED5 = 40% gamal leaf extract, the highest inhibition of *Fusarium oxysporum* was 84.67% and at a concentration of ED5 = leaf extract gamal 40% obtained the highest percentage of inhibition of *Cercospora capsici* was 87.73%. The concentration of gamal leaf extract 20% and 40% of the inhibition of each fungus is equivalent to the synthetic fungicide Benlox 50 WP

Key words: Gamal leaf extract, vegetable fungicide, pathogenic fungi

INTRODUCTION

Chili pepper is important yet susceptible plant in agriculture sector as it could be completely damaged by many pathogen including fungi, bacteria, and virus [1, 2]. The gamal plant (*Gliricidia maculata*) is native to the tropical Pacific Coast of Central America has been known its benefits one of which is the bioactivity. Leaf extract of the gamal plant has biological properties, including as antifungal, rodenticide, and botanical insecticide. The results of the phytochemical analysis of gamal leaf extract showed that this extract contained secondary metabolites of alkaloids, terpenoids, steroids, and flavonoids with the most flavonoids content. The presence of these flavonoids is thought to be a toxic compound that can kill mealybugs. That flavonoid compounds are polyphenol group compounds and have potential as antioxidants and have other benefits, including antifungal agents [3].

The application of gamal leaf extract on the growth of the *Vibrio* sp. has been bactericide at a concentration of 40% with inhibitory activity of 1.5 mm where the sig. (p-value) of 5.87 (> 0.05) [4]. The concentration of 40% was not significantly different from the concentration of 50% or 60%. The potential of gamal leaf extract on the growth of bacteria *Flexibacter maritimus* reported that the concentration of 60% with an inhibitory power of 2 mm where the sig. (p-value) of 33.00 (> 0.05), the concentration of 60% was significantly different from the concentration of 50%, 40%, and 30%. It was concluded that the extract of gamal leaves had potential as bactericide against *Vibrio* sp. and *Flexibacter maritimum*. The polar extract (water and methanol) of gamal leaves contains flavonoid compounds which act as botanical insecticides against mealybugs on coffee plants with an LC50 value at 72 hours for 0.033% water extract and methanol extract. 0.039% [5].

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Integrated pest control (IPM), in Indonesia continues to be improved in the development and cultivation of crops by farmers. The attack of pests and plant diseases is an important limiting factor in the effort to increase the production of cultivated crops, including chili. The province of North Sumatra has produced red chili production in the last four years experiencing fluctuations in production, namely 2012: 197,411 tons, 2013: 161,933 tons, 2014: 147,812 ton. When viewed from the data from the national statistical center agency in 2014, the production of red chili peppers in North Sumatra Province decreased by 14,123 tons or 8.72% compared to 2013. One of the causes of the decline in the production of red chili is anthracnose, fusarium wilt, and leaf spot cercospora.

According to Efri, 2010, the loss caused by disease *Colletotrichum capsici* reaches 70%, even anthracnose can reduce the production of chili plants by 100% if it is supported by wet conditions, lots of rain, and humidity. In addition, the attack of fusarium wilt is caused by the fungus *Fusarium sp*, causing losses of horticultural plant products reaching 40% for the Asian region [6]. The rate of spread of fungi is fusarium very fast and can spread to other plants by infecting plant roots using sprouts or mycelium tubes through water. Apart from these two fungi, it can also be seen that in Indonesia the loss of crop production due to leaf spot disease *Cercospora* in chilies ranges from 30-40%.

Until now, the disease control has used chemical pesticides. Thirty percent of pesticides are discarded to the ground during the dry season and 80% in the rainy season are disposed of in the water [7]. Excessive use of chemical pesticides has a negative impact on the environment and humans. As well as disturbing the natural balance which causes pests to become resistant and a threat to predators, parasites, fish, birds, and wildlife contaminated with pesticides.

Based on the description above, research was carried out on the bioactivity test of gamal leaf extract (*Gliricidia maculata*) as a bio fungicide against several pathogenic fungi (*Colletotrichum capsici*, *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Cercospora capsici*) the cause of disease in red chilies (*Capsicum annum L.*). We investigated to determine the concentration of the effectiveness of gamal leaf extract (*Gliricidia maculata*) as a bio fungicide against several pathogenic fungi (*Colletotrichum capsici*, *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Cercospora capsici*) the cause of disease in red chili plants (*Capsicum annum L.*).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Sample Collecting and Fungi Culture

Samples was collected from the heap of gamal Leaves on Jalan Kolam Medan. Fresh Gamal leaves are weighed as much as 100 grams. The dried gamal leaves are then mashed and refined in beaker glass with the addition of 100 ml distilled water for 1 hour. Then the top layer of the extract is taken 100 ml which will be used for toxicity testing.

Isolation of *C. capsici* obtained from chilies that show anthracnose symptoms. Fruit parts showing anthracnose symptoms are cut to a size of $\pm 0.5 \times 0.5$ cm² and soaked in 70% alcohol for 2.5 minutes to reduce contaminants from other organisms. The chilies are rinsed with clean water and dried using a tissue. The chili was then grown on PDA media in petri dishes and incubated for ± 7 days at room temperature 26–28°C. After incubation, microscopic identification of the fungal conidia was carried out.

In-vitro analysis of Clicidia leaf extract

Inhibition test gamal leaf extract against *C. capsici* in vitro carried out in petri dishes using cultured fungus. By mixing the gamal leaf extract according to the treatment concentration into PDA media and then sterilizing it (in positive control, gamal leaf extract was not added while in negative control mixed into PDA media was synthetic fungicide). After that, in the middle of the frozen PDA media, cut of placed *C. capsici* was a 10 mm

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diameter. After incubation for 7 days, observations were made by measuring the inhibition of *C. Capsici* growth.

Observations to calculate the inhibition of fungal growth *C capsici* on petri dishes were In-vitro carried out by measuring the colony diameter perpendicular to the diameter so that the average colony diameter was obtained *C. capsici*. The data obtained is then used to calculate the diameter of *C. capsici* with the following formula: $D = [D1 - D2] / 2$ where: D = Diameter of *C. capsici* (mm), $D1$ = Diameter *C. Capsici* is perpendicular to the top, $D2$ = The diameter of *C. capsici* is perpendicular to the side

In-Vivo Analysis

In vivo was performed using a non-factorial randomized block design (no factorial shelves) with a treatment factor of Gamal Leaf extract obtained from the results of in experiments vitro in the laboratory. The treatment levels were carried out in the experiment in vivo with the extract concentration level below the effective concentration. Treatment repetitions and the number of treatment samples to be carried out based on the results of the concentration to be applied and determining the level in the Non-Factorial Randomized Block Design (Non-factorial RBD).

Gamal leaf extract solution to be applied in the field is added to the solution. Application I was carried out when the plants were 100 dpi, Application II was carried out when the plants were 120 dpi, Application III was carried out when the plants were 130 days after planting, Application IV was carried out at the time Plants aged 140 dpi, Application V was carried out when the plants were 160 dpi. Application of gamaldehyde extract solution is carried out using a hand sprayer by spraying on the plants, this bio fungicide is carried out in the afternoon.

Analysis Method

After the research data is obtained, data analysis will be carried out using a Non-Factorial Completely Randomized Design (CRD) with the following formula:

$$y_{ijk} = \mu + A_i + \sum_{ijk}$$

Description:

Y_{ij} = The observed value of the i -th treatment in the j -group

μ = the general average value of

A_i = the effect of the i -treatment (1, 2, 3, 4, 5)

\sum_{ij} = experimental error from the i th treatment to the j -observation.

If the results of this study have a significant effect, then further testing is carried out with the Duncan distance test, and if this research does not have a significant effect then there is no need for further testing.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In-vitro analysis

In the in-vitro, the parameters of colony diameter, morphology and colony characteristics were observed from each extract treatment (Figure 1). The parameters of the observations carried out during the study for the application of bio fungicide extract of gamal leaves on chili plants consisted of; vegetative parameters (plant height, number of branches, flower age, harvest and intensity of fungal attack (Appendix 6), attack intensity is calculated using the formula $IS = [\sum (nxV) / (ZxN)] \times 100\%$, where IS = intensity of attack, n = the number of fruit for each class of spotting, V = the score for each class of spotting, N = the number of fruit observed, and Z

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= the highest score for the area of the spot class, with the damage values as follows: 0 = no attack symptoms, 1 = area fruit damage > 0-5%, 2 = fruit damage area > 5-15%, 3 = fruit damage area > 15-30%, 4 = fruit damage area > 30%

Gambar 1. Diameter Growth of *Colletotrichum capsici*, *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Cercospora capsici* Fungal Colonies Against Gamal Leaf Extract (*Gliricidia maculata*)

The inhibition of colony diameter growth of the three fungi, namely, *Colletotrichum capsici*, *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Cercospora capsici* was affected by the presence of secondary metabolite compounds possessed by gamal leaves which are anti-fungal. Anti-fungal compounds have various inhibitory mechanisms against fungal cells. Anti-fungal compounds have a mechanism of action by neutralizing enzymes involved in fungal invasion and colonization, damaging fungal cell membranes, inhibiting fungal enzyme systems so that they interfere with the formation of hyphal tips and affect the synthesis of nucleic acids and proteins [8].

5.5. In Vivo Observations.

Observation results and processing of variance data showed that the application of gamal leaf extract and synthetic fungicides did not significantly affect the height of the chili plants. The results of the assay of gamal leaf extract as a bio functionality are presented in Table 1. Based on Table 7 shows that there is no significant effect on the height of the chili plants given gamal leaf extract as a bio fungicide against anthracnose. But definitively, the treatment of gamal leaf extract 70% or AF3 showed the best results.

Table 1. Effect Gamal Leaf Extract on Red Chili Plant Height 3-10 MST (Transformation Results $\sqrt{x + 0.5}$).

Threatment	Chilli pepper growth (Week Post-Planting)							
	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
AF-	3,47 tn	4,31 tn	4,69 tn	5,64 tn	6,03 tn	6,31 tn	6,56 tn	6,73 tn
AF+	3,66 tn	4,49 tn	5,04 tn	5,72 tn	6,08 tn	6,39 tn	6,85 tn	6,99 tn
AF1	3,91 tn	4,58 tn	5,19 tn	5,81 tn	6,36 tn	6,68 tn	6,99 tn	7,17 tn
AF2	3,87 tn	4,70 tn	5,32 tn	6,01 tn	6,40 tn	6,78 tn	7,07 tn	7,27 tn
AF3	3,98 tn	4,87 tn	5,40 tn	6,11 tn	6,46 tn	6,83 tn	7,13 tn	7,32 tn

Note: Numbers followed by the same letter in the same column show insignificant differences at the 99% (lowercase) and 99% (uppercase) levels.

This is presumably because the secondary metabolites have not acted in controlling *C. capsici*, the cause of the ineffectiveness of giving gamal leaf extract on the height of chili plants is due to the high temperature observation. High temperatures can cause a high evaporation process. This is in accordance with the statement conveyed the weaknesses of pesticides based on essential oils and natural ingredients are related to the properties of essential oils and the water content itself which is volatile and unstable or not resistant to sunlight.

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5.5.2. Number of Chili Plant Branches.

Unlike the case with the data processed from variance, it shows that the application of gamal leaf extract and synthetic fungicides significantly affects the number of chili plant branches. The results of the assay of gamal leaf extract as a biofunctionality are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. The Effect Gamal Leaf Extract on the Number of Branches of Red Chili Plants 3-10 MST (Transformation Result $\sqrt{x + 0.5}$).

Threatment	Chilli pepper growth (Week Post-Planting)							
	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
AF-	3,01 tn	3,41 tn	3,52 b	3,73 b C	4,21 c B	4,82 c B	5,19 c B	5,25 c C
AF+	3,53 tn	3,90 tn	4,47 a	4,64 a AB	5,02 b A	5,45 b A	5,84 b A	5,93 b AB
AF1	3,54 tn	4,01 tn	4,64 ab	4,87 a A	5,20 ab A	5,51 b A	5,79 b B	5,89 b B
AF2	2,93 tn	3,39 tn	3,96 a	3,96 b BC	4,95 b A	5,73 b A	5,87 b A	5,95 b A
AF3	2,72 tn	3,59 tn	4,45 a	4,92 a A	5,39 a A	6,03 a A	6,54 a A	6,59 a A

Note: Numbers followed by the same letter in the same column show insignificant differences at the 95% (lowercase) and 99% (uppercase) levels.

Based on these data, it was found that giving gamal leaf extract could suppress the development of infection *C. capsici* in the experiment by showing the increase in the number of chili plant branches. The results of the variance test at the 95% and 99% levels showed that it was significantly different at 5-10 MST. The difference that increased 6-10 MST was in the AF3 treatment (70% concentration) which was not significantly different from the AF2 and AF + treatments, but was very significantly different from the AF-treatment. The AF-treatment is the lowest treatment, this is because the chili plants do not use gamal leaf extract or synthetic fungicides, thus affecting the increase in the number of chili peppers. Suryotomo (2006) states that the development of anthracnose if not treated like synthetic fungicides will accelerate the development of this disease and cause the disease to develop in plant tissues. In contrast to chili plants that are given gamal leaf extract will be able to inhibit the development of anthracnose disease, which can be seen in Table 5 the higher the concentration of gamal leaf extract, the more it can inhibit the development of fungi *C. capsici*. where according to Muta'ali and Kristanti (2015), which states that the higher the provision of essential compounds, the more effective it is in inhibiting pests and diseases attacking a plant [9]. The weaknesses of essential oil-based pesticides are related to the properties of the essential oil itself which are volatile and unstable or not resistant to sunlight [10]

This is because the compounds contained in gamal leaves can inhibit the growth of *C. capsici*. The content of gamal leaves contains secondary metabolite compounds including flavonoids, saponins, tannins, alkaloids, and steroids / triterpenoids. That flavonoid compounds have a number of uses. First, against plants, namely as a regulator of plants, regulator of photosynthesis, and can be used as a vegetable pesticide because it works as an antimicrobial and antiviral agent [11].

Tannin compounds contained in gamal leaves are antibacterial that the ethanol extract of gamal leaves can be used as antibacterial against *Streptococcus mutans* and *Escherichia coli*. While the antifungal compounds are saponins, saponins contained in gamal leaves can be antibacterial and, the presence of saponins can be an indicator of the resistance of a plant species to fungal infection. Saponins are surfactants that are polar in shape so that they break down the fat layer on the cell membrane which in turn causes interference with cell membrane permeability, this results in the diffusion of materials or substances needed by the fungus can be disturbed, eventually the cells swell and break, so that they cannot cause the growth of fungi *C. capsici*.

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Age of Flower Appearance

Based on the results of variance, it showed that the application of gamal leaf extract and synthetic fungicides significantly affected the production of chili fruit at the second harvest. The results of the assay of gamal leaf extract as a biofunctionality are presented in Table 3. Based on Table 6 shows that the best treatment for chili plant production in and 2 is in the AF3 treatment (70%) gamal leaf extract which is not different from AF2 treatment (60%). Gamal leaf extract was compared with AF1 treatment (50%) gamal leaf extract, AF + synthetic fungicide, and AF- without treatment with either 95% or 99% confidence levels.

Table 3. Effect of Giving Gamal Leaf Extract on Flowering Age of Chili Plants on the 1st and 2nd Harvest.

threatment	Chilli pepper growth	
	Harvesting	Harvesting Ke-2
AF-	8,22 tn	9,19 b B
AF+	8,15 tn	9,03 b B
AF1	7,97 tn	8,93 b B
AF2	7,85 tn	8,79 a B
AF3	7,74 tn	8,74 a A

Note: Numbers followed by the same letter in the same column show insignificant differences at the 95% (lowercase) and 99% (uppercase) levels.

The response curve of the relationship between the administration of gamal leaf extract and the age at which the flowers appeared at the 2nd Harvest. From Figure 7 it can be seen that the shape of the response curve of the relationship between the application of gamal leaf extract and the age at which the flowers appear on the 2nd Harvest is linear, with the equation: $Y = -0.1134x + 9.2766$. The regression coefficient (R^2) = 0.97 explained that the 97% interest appear age caused by the effect of gamal leaf extract.

This is due to the content of secondary metabolite compounds found in gamal leaves that can inhibit the growth of fungi *C. capsici*. The secondary metabolic found in plants is self-defense against microorganisms (bacteria, fungi, protozoa), insects and herbivores. The content of gamal leaves contains secondary metabolites, including flavonoids, saponins, tannins, alkaloids, and steroids / triterpenoids.

One of the secondary metabolites that greatly influence the development offungi *C. capsici* is saponins compounds. The mechanism of saponins as an antimicrobial causes protein and enzyme leakage in cells. Plants containing secondary metabolic compounds, especially saponins, will be more resistant to disease, where the principle of saponins is similar to detergents, as a result, it will affect the decrease in surface tension of bacterial cell walls and damage membrane permeability [12]. The destruction to the membrane wall offungi *C. capsici* will disrupt the survival of the fungus [13].

Not only saponin compounds that inhibit the development of fungi, *C. capsici* but also tananin compounds found in gamal leaf extract works by depositing proteins and damaging cell membranes so that fungal growth is inhibited. Tannin compounds are organic compounds that actively inhibit microbial growth by damaging microbial cell walls and forming bonds with microbial cell functional proteins [14]. The antimicrobial mechanism of tannins is inhibiting the synthesis of chitin which is used for cell wall formation so that fungal growth is inhibited.

Chili Production

Based on the results of variance, it showed that the application of gamal leaf extract and synthetic fungicides significantly affected the production of chili fruit. The results of the assay of gamal leaf extract as a bio functionality are presented in Table 6. Based on Table 4 shows that the best treatment for chili plant production at the 1st and 2nd harvests was found in AF3 treatment (70%) of gamal leaf extract which was not different

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with treatment AF2 (60%) gamal leaf extract was compared with AF1 (50%) gamal leaf extract treatment, AF + synthetic fungicide, and AF- without treatment with either 95% or 99% confidence levels.

Tabel 4. The Effect of Giving Gamal Leaf Extract on the Production of Chili Fruit from the 1st and 2nd Harvest (Transformation Results $\sqrt{x + 0.5}$)

Pelakuan	Produksi Buah Cabai	
	Panen Ke-1	Panen Ke-2
AF-	1,99 c B	2,18 c C
AF+	2,82 ab A	2,70 b B
AF1	2,74 b A	2,72 b B
AF2	2,91 a A	3,18 a A
AF3	3,09 a A	3,18 a A

Note: Numbers followed by the same letter in the same column show insignificant differences at the 95% (lowercase) and 99% (uppercase) levels.

This is because the content of secondary metabolic compounds found in gamal leaves can inhibit the growth of the fungal mycelium *C. capsici*, which according to Naim (2004), which states that secondary metabolic found in plants is self-defense against microorganisms (bacteria, fungi, protozoa), insects and herbivores. According to (Arifin 2014; Rahayu and Pukan, 1998) that the content of gamal leaves contains secondary metabolites, including flavonoids, saponins, tannins, alkaloids, and steroids / triterpenoids. Flavonoid compounds have a number of uses. First, against plants, namely as a regulator of plants, regulator of photosynthesis, and can be used as a vegetable pesticide because it works as an antimicrobial and antiviral agent [15].

Onset Intensity

The intensity of anthracnose attack is the percentage ratio of the number of fruit harvested to the number of fruits attacked by anthracnose. Based on the results of variance, it showed that the application of gamal leaf extract and synthetic fungicides significantly affected the intensity of the attack. The results of the assay of gamal leaf extract as a bio functionality are presented in Table 6. Based on Table 5 shows that the best treatment of attack intensity at the 1st and 2nd harvests is in the AF3 treatment (70%) of gamal leaf extract which is not different with AF2 treatment. (60%) gamal leaf extract was compared with AF1 treatment (50%) gamal leaf extract, AF + synthetic fungicide, and AF- without treatment with either 95% or 99% confidence levels.

Table 5. The Effect of Giving Gamal Leaf Extract on the Intensity of Attack from the 1st and 2nd Harvest (Transformation Result $\sqrt{x + 0.5}$).

Perlakuan	Produksi Buah Cabai	
	Panen Ke-1	Panen Ke-2
AF-	2,12 c B	2,06 c B
AF+	1,40 b A	1,49 b AB
AF1	1,56 b AB	1,63 cb B
AF2	1,39 b A	1,18 ab A
AF3	0,97 a A	0,97 a A

Note: Numbers followed by the same letter in the same column show insignificant differences at the 95% (lowercase) and 99% (uppercase) levels.

In AF-treatment, the chili fruit had the highest intensity value of anthracnose attack because of the AF treatment, the absence of phenolic compounds, alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins was given so that the intensity of anthracnose attacks was greater than the other treatments. Secondary metabolic compounds including phenols,

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flavonoids, and saponins are compounds that damage cell walls [16]. Cell wall as a component of bacterial cell defense was damaged so that secondary metabolites could enter deeper and disturb other organelles. Furthermore, This mechanism also happen in viral infection, upon its infection viral such Geminivirus disturb the mechanism of secondary metabolite in order to hijack plant defense mechanism [17]

Phenolic compounds found in plants will cause lysis of microbial cells as well as the content of phenol compounds in gamal leave. Adding that if the microbial cell is damaged, toxins from the cell can enter and result in reduced essential metabolites needed by microbes, phenolic compounds as antimicrobials are active against vegetative microbial cells. Gamal leaf extract was effective in controlling bacteria *Streptococcus mutans*. It has been proved also that, based on previous investigation, gamal leaf extract shown optimum inhibition on three main destructive fungi in Indonesia (*Colletotrichum capsici*, *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Cercospora capsici*) with the inhibition of 82.49, 84.6, 87.73% through in-vitro analysis [18].

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of giving extracts on fungal growth media, it can be concluded that giving extract of gamal leaves (*Gliricidia maculata*) with EDtreatment with a3 concentration of 20% significantly suppressed the growth of colonies *Colletotrichum capsici* and EDtreatment with a5 concentration of 40% significantly suppressed colon growth in mushrooms. *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Cercospora capsici*

In field experiments it can be concluded that the application of jengkol bark extract has a very significant effect on the parameter of the number of branches at 5-10 MST. Meanwhile, the age parameters appear flowering and the intensity of the attack on the second harvest, while the harvest has a very significant effect on the 1st harvest and the 2nd harvest.

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